

Digital Marketing (A Theoretical Approach)

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Mr. K. Sivasubramani

Assistant Professor / MBA

K.S.R.College of Engineering (Autonomous), Tiruchengode

Ms. D. Kanchana & Ms. S. Saranya

II MBA

K.S.R.College of Engineering (Autonomous), Tiruchengode

Abstract

In this world of digital marketing, digitization is a style that is sweeping across the whole world. The trend of digital shopping is growing day by day with the concepts of Internet marketing that is turning into a great platform of digital marketing along with the electronic gadgets like the digital billboards, mobile, tablets and smartphones, gaming consoles, and many such gadgets that help in digital marketing. Flipkart, with its innovative digital marketing, has created a niche market in online stores competing with popular stores showing the power of online marketing. The case study analyzes show Flipkart.com has brought in an array of online marketing and digital strategies to achieve and make it big in the digital marketing quarter. The case also examines how Flipkart has had a large gain in the online marketing sector as they produced new penetrations into the digital marketing course. And a few times from now, it will be ultimately seen that current marketing being replaced by digital marketing. Digital shopping is going to be top on the agenda of many marketers, and they might be looking for innovative ways to reduce cost per lead, market online, increase click-through-rates and conversion rates and discover what's hot in digital shopping.

Introduction of Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is the marketing of stocks or help using digital technologies, mainly on the Internet, but also holding free phones, any other digital medium, and display advertising. Digital marketing courses are methods based on the internet that can create, accelerate, and transmit result value from producer to the final customer by digital networks.

Digital marketing's growth since the 1990s and 2000s has changed the way brands, and businesses use technology for marketing. As digital platforms are normally held in purchasing plans and everyday life, and as characters use digital marketing campaigns, digital devices instead of visiting physical shops are becoming more popular and useful.

Digital shopping methods such as search engine optimization (SEO), content marketing, influencer marketing, search engine marketing (SEM), campaign marketing, content automation, data-driven marketing, social media marketing, e-commerce marketing,

e-mail direct marketing, social media optimization, Display advertising, optical disks and e-books, and games are becoming more common in our advancing technology.

New Non – Linear Marketing Approach

To engage consumers, retailers must shift from a linear marketing approach of one-way communication to a value exchange model of mutual discussion and benefit-sharing between provider and consumer. Exchanges are more non-linear, free-flowing, and both one-to-many or one-on-one. The spread of awareness and information can occur across numerous channels, such as YouTube, blogosphere, Instagram, Facebook, Pinterest, Snapchat, and a variety of other platforms.

The Nielsen Global Connected Commerce Survey attended meetings in 26 countries to observe how customers are applying the Internet to make purchasing choices in online and stores. Online shoppers are frequently looking to purchase internationally, with over 50% in the study who obtained online in the last six months saying they got from an overseas retailer.

SEO (Search Engine Optimization) Policies

- Minimum contract period (6months)
- Weekly work report to be submitted at every Sunday
- Monthly work report to be presented at 1st of every month
- Monthly keyword rank report to be presented at 1st of every month
- Website traffic report from google analytic to be submitted at 1st of every month
- Meeting to be conducted every week to know the current flow of the work

BRAND Knowledge

EASE OF ENTRANCE

A key goal is appealing to digital shopping consumers and delivery of digital media and allowing them to communicate with the brand through servicing. Learning is easy to access at a fast rate through the use of digital information. Users with entrance to the Internet can use many digital mediums, such as YouTube, Facebook, Email, and Forums, etc.

Competitive Advantage

By using Internet platforms, businesses can create an aggressive position within different midpoints. To reach the maximum potential of digital purchasing, firms use traditional media as its central tool to create a channel of information.

Effectiveness

Make awareness has been proven to work with more effectiveness in mountains that are high in question escape. Also, these countries that have change avoidance; social media marketing works effectively.

Latest Development and Approaches

One of the main changes that occurred in traditional marketing was the “emergence of digital marketing.”

Segmentation: more focus has been installed on segmentation within digital marketing, to target specific markets in both business-to-business and business-to-consumer sectors.

Influencer marketing: Important nodes are treated within related communities, known as influencers. That is growing an essential concept in digital targeting. It is likely to reach influencers via paid advertising, such as Google Adwords campaigns, or Facebook Advertising or through

refined sCRM (social customer relationship management) software, such as SAP C4C, Microsoft Dynamics.

Online behavioral advertising: It is the method of getting knowledge about a user’s online movement above time, “on a particular device and unrelated websites, across different, to deliver announcements tailored to that preferences and user’s attention

Collaborative Environment: A collaborative atmosphere can be set up between the company, the technology service provider, and resource sharing, the digital agencies to optimize effort, communications, and reusability.

Data-driven promoting: Users generate a lot of data in every step they take on the path of the customer journey, and Brands can now use that data to activate their known audience with data-driven programmatic media buying.

Remarketing: Remarketing performs a principal role in digital purchasing. This tactic allows marketers to issue targeted commercials in the face of an interest classification or a distinguished audience, usually called searchers in web speak, they have either searched for particular goods or visited or services a website for some purpose.

Game promotion: Game ads are advertisements that exist within video games or Computer. One of the most popular examples of in-game advertising is billboards looking in fun games. In-game ads also might appear as brand-name goods like cars, guns, or clothing that exist as gaming status symbols.

Ways to Further Increase the Effectiveness of Digital Marketing

A plan that is connected to the effectiveness of digital marketing is content marketing. Content marketing can be succinctly defined as “giving the content that your viewers are seeking in the places that they are asking for it. That is enough to content marketing, building your brand more relevant to the target customers, as well as more visible to the target customer.

- Interesting mail titles
- Establishment of customer exclusivity
- Low Technical Requirements:
- Rewards

Strategy

Stages of Planning

Using Dr. Dave Chaffey’s approach, digital shopping planning (DMP) has three main stages: Strategy, Opportunity, and Action. He suggests that any business looking to implement a successful digital marketing plan must structure their plan by looking at strategy, opportunity, and action.

Opening

To create an effective DMP, a company first needs to review the marketplace and set ‘SMART’ (Specific, Actionable, Measurable, Relevant, and Time-Bound) objectives.

Approach

To create a planned digital strategy, the company must review their digital project (what you are offering to consumers) and communicate it using digital customer targeting methods.

Activity

The third and final stage needs the firm to set a budget and management systems; these must be combined touchpoints, such as audience reached across all digital programs. Furthermore, marketers must secure the budget and management systems are integrating the owned, paid, and earned media of the company.

Courses

Digital marketing is supported by many shippers. As a businessperson, one's core objective is to find passages a better overall ROI for the brand and which result in maximum two-way transmission There are multiple digital marketing channels available namely;

- Affiliate marketing
- Display advertising
- Email marketing
- Search engine marketing
- Social Media Marketing
- Social networking service
- Online public relations
- Video advertising

Self-Regulation

- The ICC Code has combined rules that apply to market communications using digital interactive media throughout the guidelines.
- Clear and crystalline mechanisms to enable consumers to choose not to have their data collected for advertising or marketing purposes;
- Clear evidence that a social material site is commercial and is under the control or influence of a marketer;
- Limits are designed so that marketers communicate soon only when there are reasonable grounds to conclude that the user has an interest in what is happening offered;
- Special care and protection for children.

Advantages and Limitations

- The whole idea of digital marketing can be a very significant aspect of the overall communication between the consumer and the organization.
- Another benefit of digital marketing is that consumers are provided to the brand and the product that is being sold directly.
- To clarify the display is easy to access as well it can be reached at any time any place.
- Another advantage is that digital shopping is easy to be measured allowing companies to know the reach that their shopping is making, whether the digital shopping is working or not and the amount of activity and discussion that is involved.
- Two other practical conditions can be seen in the case of digital marketing. One, digital shopping is useful for specific categories of products, meaning only consumer goods can be done through digital channels

Understanding the Market

One way marketers can reach out to customers, and understand their thought process is through what is called an empathy map. An empathy map is a four-step method. The first step is through asking problems that the consumer would be thinking in their demographic. The second step is to describe the feelings that the consumer may be having.

Sharing Economy

The "sharing economy" refers to an industrial pattern that aims to obtain a resource that is not enough used. Nowadays, the sharing market has had an unimagined effect on many common elements, industry, including labor, and distribution system. This effect is not negligible that some

businesses are clearly under threat. The sharing economy is changing the traditional marketing channels by changing the nature of some specific concept, including ownership, assets, and recruitment.

Digital marketing channels and conventional shopping channels are similar in function that the value of the goods or service is passed from the original producer to the end-user by a kind of groceries chain. For example, a typical digital marketing channel is email. The system can refresh the activity or advertising information to the user by subscribing the newsletter mail that happened in consuming. In addition to this typical approach, the built-in control, efficiency, and low cost of digital marketing channels is an essential feature in the application of sharing economy.

Conclusion

The conclusion of digital marketing has now converted a hot topic for discussion. Modern technology has changed a lot. Besides the growth of modern technology, the system of businesses has also changed. In this regard, digital marketing comes to take the leading position. The modern generation does not want to go to any shop or shopping mall to buy anything. They want to buy everything online. So, various companies always try to stay attached to their consumers or customers via the internet. To get the best of it, consumers and marketers must know the advantage and disadvantage of digital marketing

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